

Sedimentation studies of Kangsabati reservoir and some physico-chemical investigations of reservoir water and sediments

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Sedimentation studies of Kangsabati reservoir have been made to measure the performance of the river and examine the quality of water and sediment for judging their utility in agronomy. The results suggest that sediment deposition is not alarming. Water quality of the reservoir is good for irrigation purposes. Sediment is rich in nutrients and can be used in agronomy.

A reservoir is usually constructed to receive excess flow of river water during rainy season for storage. The purpose is : (i) to save the excess or unwanted water during rainy season and utilise a portion of water for irrigation purposes during the lean period and increase agricultural production and (ii) to control flood effectively.

A number of reservoirs (Maithon, Tilaiya, Mayurakshi etc.) were constructed during the last fifty years. It is apparent that the receiving of water is accompanied by sediment deposition which in the long run reduces the storage capacity to annul the beneficial operations of the reservoir i.e., storage and distribution of water, flood control measures etc. The life span of these reservoirs are very much dependent on the rate of sedimentation of the reservoirs. Naturally, occasional capacity survey of the dams are prerequisite for the proper running of the reservoirs. Thus, monitoring of sediment deposition at regular intervals are undertaken : (i) to compare the performance of the reservoir vis-a-vis the original estimation by comparative sedimentation study, (ii) to suggest effective measures to control sedimentation, (iii) to examine the water and sediment quality of the reservoir and (iv) to examine whether desilting process may be undertaken and sediments can be utilised in agronomy.

Sediments accumulated at the reservoir beds are sinks for many materials transported from the land by the river water. Many substances that occur naturally such as exchangeable ions (like Na⁺, K⁺, Ca²⁺ etc.) and nutrients (like N, P etc.) are expected to be mobilised in sediments as a result of natural processes and human activities.

Due to soil erosion and unscientific discharge of wastes from sources manifold, the rivers are expected to trans-

port enormous amounts of dissolved and suspended solids which cause heavy siltation. Naturally, the siltation causes enormous mobilisation of essential nutrients. Sediment quality of the river Ganga suggests the suitability of sediments for agronomy¹⁻⁵. The values of the constituents can be converted to kg/ha multiplying ppm values by 2.24 as one hectare furrow slice soil weighs 2.24×10^6 kg.

A number of technical reports are available on the River Behavior and Control (Published by River Research Institute)⁶⁻¹⁰. Recently, De published two important reports on the estimation of life of some reservoirs of West Bengal and a comparative sedimentation study on Mayurakshi reservoir^{11,12}. The Kangsabati is relatively recent and the River Research Institute, West Bengal, initiated studies on the sedimentation rate for the Kangsabati reservoir to examine the life span and efficiency of the project.

The present work is the outcome of such studies. In addition to the determination of sedimentation, efforts have been made to study the physico-chemical qualities of the water for irrigation and sediment quality for their possible use in agronomy.

The results of investigation are presented in this communication.

Results and discussion

*Kangsabati river and reservoir*¹⁰ :

The Kangsabati river originated from Jabarband in the hills of the Chotonagpur range about 48 km, north west of Purulia town. The river flows generally in south-eastern direction through the districts of Purulia, Bankura, and Medinipur (W and E) for a course of 370

Fig. 1. Index map of the Kangsabati and Kumari catchments.

kms and ultimately falls into the Hoogly (through Haldi) near Haldia in Medinipur (East). The principal tributary in the upper reach is the river Kumari which meets the Kangsabati near Ambikanagar in Bankura. A sketch of the reservoir is shown in Fig. 1.

The river valley along its course may be sub-divided into five divisions viz. (a) Mountainous, (b) Sub-Mountainous, (c) Trough, (d) Alluvial and (e) Deltaic. The Purulia portion of the river course (135 kms) may be called as mountainous, the river slope is about 7.5 m/km and upto the dam site the course may be termed as sub-mountainous. The river slope is about 1.1 m/km.

The upper catchment of the Kangsabati river is in bad state of deforestation and denudation. The western part of the state of West Bengal is relatively arid compared to other areas, having an average annual rainfall of about 125 cm. The soil is residual, lateritic excepting loamy flood plains.

Ground water use is restrictive due to hydro-geological constraints. The distribution of rainfall during the cropping season is poor. The Kangsabati project was envisaged to supplement the water deficit for Kharif paddy and Rabi by irrigation and to mitigate the ravages of flood in its lower valley downstream of Medinipur town. An earthen dam was proposed at the confluence of the Kangsabati and Kumari at Mukutmonipur in Bankura. The Kangsabati and Kumari reservoirs are separated by a hillock. The Kangsabati portion was completed in 1964 and

the first filling was done in 1964-65 while the Kumari started to function in 1975-76. The target irrigation command of the project was 4020 sq. km and the existing effective command is 2480 sq. km in the district of Bankura, Medinipur (W) and some parts of Hoogly.

Salient features of Kangsabati portion of the twin reservoir⁶:

Catchment area	:	1606 sq. km (620 sq. mile)
Water spread of reservoir	:	57 sq. km (22 sq. mile)
Sediment contributing catchment	:	1549 sq. km (598 sq. mile)
Capacity of the reservoir	:	49892 ha-m (405297 acre-ft.)
Year of first filling of reservoir	:	1964-65 (Predam survey)

Estimation of life of reservoir :

An approximate estimation of the life of reservoir (i.e. the number of years required for the reservoir capacity to be fully depleted by sedimentation) may be made using Taylor's method i.e.

$$V_n = V_0 \cdot R^n \quad (1)$$

where V_0 = capacity of the reservoir before impounding of water, V_n = capacity of the reservoir after n years of impounding, R = ratio of reservoir capacity at the end of one year to that of the previous year, and mean annual

rate of siltation = $(1-R) \times 100\%$, R is assumed to be constant.

However, De^{11,12} observed that the effective life of reservoir estimates using Taylor's equation gives abnormally high values for the Mayurkshi reservoir and hence the method of estimation actually serves no useful purpose. No. attempt has therefore, been made to estimate the life of Kangsabati reservoir using eq. (1).

% Capacity of the reservoir with time is presented in Fig. 2. In the sedimentation survey of 1993-94 and 2000-2001 loss in capacity has been found to be 9.22% in 29 years and 10.06% in 36 years respectively. It is apparent

Fig. 2. Kangsabati reservoir. Catchment area 1606 sq. km. Initial capacity : dead storage 6507 Ha-m, live storage 43385 Ha-m and total storage 49892 Ha-m.

Table 1. Results of the chemical analysis of the water samples collected from the Kangsabati reservoir (2001)

Lab. Sl. no.	Location	Position in respect of reservoir	pH	Suspended load (ppm)	Total dissolved solids (ppm)	Chloride (Cl ⁻) (ppm)	Total hardness (ppm) (as CaCO ₃)
C-1/01	C/S-2	Front	8.1	-	96	18	135
C-2/01	C/S-3	Do	8.1	-	88	16	110
C-3/01	C/S-4	Do	8.1	56	98	17	95
C-4/01	C/S-5	Do	8.1	-	100	15	95
C-5/01	C/S-6	Do	7.5	-	80	17	120
C-6/01	C/S-7	Do	8.0	74	110	17	135
C-7/01	C/S-8	Do	7.5	-	56	14	95
C-8/01	C/S-9	Middle	7.9	-	88	15	115
C-9/01	C/S-10	Do	8.0	-	68	13	95
C-10/01	C/S-11	Do	8.1	-	-	14	100
C-11/01	C/S-12	Do	8.1	83	74	12	140
C-12/01	C/S-14	Do	8.1	-	-	13	95
C-13/01	C/S-15	Back	7.4	-	62	12	90
C-14/01	C/S-16	Do	7.5	-	100	13	80
C-15/01	C/S-17	Do	7.5	135	82	16	100

Fig. 3. Particle size distribution curves of the Kangsabati sediments : (O) Kangsabati 4/01, (Δ) 7/01 and (▽) 2/01.

Table 2. Plant nutrients in sediments of Kangsabati

Sample	Year of collection	Submergence under water	Maximum depth of water when the reservoir is full (m)	Agricultural past of sediment	Soil description	Clay % (below 2 micron)	pH	Soluble salts (g/l)	Organic carbon %	Available nitrogen (kg/hectare)	Phosphorus (as P ₂ O ₅) (kg/hectare)	Potassium (as K ₂ O) (kg/hectare)
1/01	2001	Continuous	18.3	Virgin	Yellowish brown Loamy clay	-	6.4	-	0.33	415	51	581
2/01	"	"	24.4	"	Yellowish brown clay	59.1	6.0	0.259	0.23	334	42	498
3/01	"	"	21.3	"	Yellowish brown clay	-	6.0	0.140	0.03	309	59	457
4/01	"	"	18.3	"	Yellowish brown Loamy clay	31.3	7.3	-	0.39	215	-	266
5/01	"	"	15.2	"	Yellowish brown Loamy clay	-	6.7	-	0.29	211	-	374
6/01	"	Occasional	12.2	Nearly virgin	Yellowish brown Loamy clay	-	6.0	-	0.36	267	54	315
7/01	"	"	13.7	Natural Vegetation viz. grass etc.	Yellowish brown Loamy clay	20.6	-	0.048	0.66	267	18	166
8/01	"	"	13.7	"	"	18.4	-	0.068	0.42	213	54	133
9/01	"	"	6.1	"	Yellowish brown Loamy sand	13.2	-	-	0.69	262	15	166
10/01	"	"	1.0	"	Yellowish silty sand-trace clay	3.2	-	-	0.42	217	19	124

that the rate of sedimentation can not be regarded to be alarmingly high and there is a decreasing trend.

Water analysis :

The results of the physico-chemical tests of water samples (Table 1) show that the pH values are above 7 meaning that the reservoir water is slightly alkaline. The values of dissolved solids fluctuate from 56 to 110 ppm at different cross-section. The chloride content values vary from 12 to 18 ppm and the values, in general, appear to be more near the front of reservoir in comparison with those in the back portion. The low dissolved solid of the reservoir water indicates that the water is good for irrigation purpose and any problem like salinity hazard etc. is not likely with the prolonged use of the impounded water of the reservoir.

Sediment analysis :

The mechanical analysis (grain size) of some sediments samples is presented in Fig. 3. The samples (1/01 to 5/01) indicate that the yellowish-brown sediments are basically loamy clay with clay percentage nearly 30 and are expected to be in CI-CH group as per IS classification system. The sediment samples of the occasionally submerged areas (i.e. 6/01 to 10/01) are loamy clay to sand with some fines. The sample contains less clay percentage towards the back of the reservoir. These soils are mostly CL as per IS classification.

The chemical analysis on the sediment sample (1/01 to 5/01) (Table 2) collected from deeper zones of the reservoir indicate that these are mildly acidic ($\text{pH} < 7$). The values of organic carbon percent are below 0.5 meaning low. The values of available nitrogen are low to medium while those of the available phosphorous are medium. The values of available K are high, in general, in comparison with this sediments collected from the accessible, occasionally submerged areas containing less nutrient values.

Conclusion :

The followings are the conclusion of the present work. (i) it is apparent that rate of sedimentation cannot be regarded to be alarmingly high and there is a decreasing trend, (ii) considering soluble salt, hardness, chloride content and pH of the reservoir water, it may be inferred that it is good for irrigation purposes, (iii) the run-off running down the catchment carries much of the plant nutrients with dislodged particles and these get deposited in the reservoir and so, the sediment is exploitable due to high clay content and good plant nutrient values (N-P-K) though the nutrients are much less than those present in Ganga sediments^{2,3}.

Overall speaking the fines (clay + silt) are higher near the deeper zone in comparison with the location away from the dam., i.e. near the entry of the river into the reservoir.

Experimental

Sample collection (both sediment and water) :

In the sedimentation survey the silt samples were collected from different locations of the reservoir of Kangsabati by the help of sample collector. The silt sample 1/01 to 5/01 were collected from the deepest point of the cross section. These samples were collected under water. The samples collected from the dry, accessible areas (occasionally submerged) of different cross sections were mixed to form some representative samples. These samples are designated as 6/01 to 10/01. These samples were subjected to laboratory tests to determine their physico-chemical characteristics.

Water samples were also collected from different cross sections (at 1' depth from surface) of the reservoirs for laboratory chemical test.

Laboratory tests (for both sediments and water) :

Mechanical or grain size analysis (by sedimentation and sieve conjointly) was conducted on soil samples collected¹³.

Chemical tests of the samples were carried out to determine their pH, organic carbon, available nitrogen, phosphorous and potassium. The methods followed for determination of organic carbon, nitrogen, phosphorus and potassium are dichromate method, kjeldahl distillation method, spectrophotometer method and flame photometer method respectively¹⁴. The index properties and chemical constituents are given in Table 2. For water analysis¹⁵, suspended solid, Cl-content and total hardness were determined gravimetrically, using Volhard's method, EDTA method respectively. Results of the chemical analysis of the water samples collected are presented in Table 1.

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